

NOTES

Synthesis and Characterisation of Rare Earth Complexes with 4-(2-Hydroxypent-2-en)-3-pyridylketimine

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THE present paper describes the synthesis and characterisation of La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm complexes with 4-(2-hydroxypent-2-en)-3'-pyridylketimine.

Experimental

Preparation of ligand : A mixture of equimolar proportion of acetylacetone and 3-aminopyridine solution in benzene was refluxed for 2 h on a oil-bath at 130°. The resulting dark red oily liquid on distillation yielded the product, b.p. 165° (Found : C, 66.98 ; H, 6.78 ; N, 15.74. C₁₀H₁₂N₂O calcd. for : C, 68.20 ; H, 6.81 ; N, 16.00%).

Results and Discussion

The complexes were found insoluble in acetone, chloroform, ethanol but soluble in DMSO. Chemical analyses (Table 1) suggest a 1 : 2 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry. The presence of the ionic chlorine is confirmed by conductivity data (Table 1) and alcoholic silver nitrate test.

The lanthanum(III) complex was diamagnetic, while the other complexes were paramagnetic. The magnetic moment values (Table 1) suggest octahedral (O_h) geometry for these complexes. The ir vibrational modes of M-O and M-N were observed respectively at 410 and 520 cm⁻¹ in the La^{III} complex, 400 and 525 cm⁻¹ in the Ce^{III} complex, 420 and 520 cm⁻¹ in the Pr^{III} complex, 415 and 490 cm⁻¹ in the Nd^{III} complex and 400 and 510 cm⁻¹ in the Sm^{III} complex¹; these bands were absent in the ligand. The 250-230 cm⁻¹ bands in the complexes may be assigned to ν_{M-Cl} . The 1580 and 1520 cm⁻¹ bands in the free ligand, assigned to sym and antisym $\nu_{C=C} + \nu_{C=N}$ of pyridine ring were replaced by new bands of higher frequency and reduced intensity in the complexes indicating metal-pyridine bonding. A sharp band at 990 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand, due to the pyridine ring breathing

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Decomposition temperature °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ_M^{**} Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ_{eff} B.M.
			M	N	Cl		
[LaL ₂]Cl	Creamy	146	25.98 (26.49)	10.40 (10.67)	6.68 (6.76)	48.20	0.35
[CeL ₂]Cl	Brown	158	26.12 (26.66)	10.48 (10.65)	6.71 (6.74)	54.29	2.34
[PrL ₂]Cl	Light brown	140	26.28 (26.77)	10.40 (10.63)	6.68 (6.73)	60.00	3.56
[NdL ₂]Cl	Creamy	150	27.10 (27.23)	10.39 (10.57)	6.62 (6.69)	57.82	3.72
[SmL ₂]Cl	Brown	144	27.59 (28.06)	10.88 (10.46)	6.57 (6.61)	58.60	1.20

*L = C₁₀H₁₁N₂O.

**In DMSO.

Preparation of complexes : A solution of lanthanide(III) chloride (10 mmol) in aqueous ethanol was treated with the ligand (10 mmol) solution in ethanol with constant stirring. In case of La^{III} and Ce^{III} pH of the solution was adjusted with NH₄OH. The resulting light coloured precipitates were digested on a water-bath for 2 h at ~70°, washed with ethanol and acetone, and dried under reduced pressure.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at 301K by Gouy's method. Ir spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

modes, shifted to lower frequency (970-975 cm⁻¹) on complexation. The 750 cm⁻¹ band in the free ligand splitted into two components 720 and 755 cm⁻¹, indicating the coordination of pyridine nitrogen to metal. The sharp ν_{OH} ligand band at 3650 cm⁻¹ disappeared on complexation confirming the coordination of the metal through the oxygen of the hydroxyl group. Coordination of nitrogen atom of the azomethine group was evident from the reduction in $\nu_{C=N}$ by 20-40 cm⁻¹ in the complexes.

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Studies on Basic Lead Sulphate Ion-exchanger. Part-I. Synthesis, Properties, Anion-exchange Behaviour and Separation of Anions

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THIS paper reports the synthesis, composition, chemical and thermal stability, pH-titration and anion-exchange behaviour of basic lead sulphate. Distribution and separation of various anions have been studied. No such study on basic lead sulphate has been reported earlier.

Experimental

Basic lead sulphate: Four different batches (B_1 , B_2 , B_3 and B_4) of basic lead sulphate were prepared by mixing $0.5M$ $Pb(NO_3)_2 + 0.5M$ $Na_2SO_4 \cdot 10H_2O / (NH_4)_2SO_4$ and $0.5M$ NH_4OH in different ratios and refluxing for different time periods. $Na_2SO_4 \cdot 10H_2O$ was used for B_1 while for the others $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ was used. The refluxing time for B_1 was 4 h and the product was allowed to stand for 24 h, filtered, washed with deionised water (pH 6.5), dried at room temperature and finally at $100 \pm 5^\circ$ for 1 h.

Lead and sulphate were then estimated by titration with standard EDTA solution¹. The water molecules present in basic lead sulphate were determined as before². The weight loss (%) at 600° were 4.7 (B_1), 4.0 (B_2), 2.0 (B_3) and 1.4 (B_4). No further weight loss occurred on heating upto 800° . The ratio of $Pb : SO_4 : H_2O$ in the products were found to be (B_1) 2 : 1 : 1.4, (B_2) 2 : 1.7 : 1.2, (B_3) 2 : 1.6 : 0.6 and (B_4) 2 : 1.6 : 0.5. The exchangers were stable towards $2.0M$ H_2SO_4 , $0.01M$ HCl , HNO_3 , CH_3COOH and $HClO_4$ and $0.1M$ $NaOH$ and NH_4OH . For column operation, 5.0 g of the exchanger in a glass column (1.1 cm i.d.) was used. All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Results and Discussion

Plots of pH against volume of added acid showed two sharp breaks³ indicating bifunctional nature of the basic ion-exchangers.

Ion-exchange capacity: The exchange capacity was determined by batch operation⁴. A constant exchange capacity was obtained for sodium chloride solution of concentration greater than $1.0M$ for which complete equilibration required 4 h. The total exchange capacity was determined at different pH by taking 0.5 g of exchanger and either 200 ml of $1M$ ($HCl + NaCl$) or $0.5M$ ($H_2SO_4 + Na_2SO_4$) with varying quantities of acid. The chloride ion-exchange capacities (meq/g) for B_1 at different equilibrium pH were 0.7 (pH 5.0), 1.7 (pH 4.4), 2.5 (pH 4.0), 2.9 (pH 3.5), and for sulphate ion the exchange capacities were 0.9 (pH 4.0), 1.2 (pH 3.4) and 2.8 (pH 3.3) indicating increases of exchange capacity with decrease of pH. Slight decrease from 2.77 to 2.55 meq/g in anion-exchange capacity was observed when heated upto 300° , but when heated to 600° the exchange capacity decreased to 1.0 meq/g. Regeneration capacity for SO_4^{2-} after 2nd regeneration was found to be 2.0 meq/g.

Column elution of hydroxyl ion: Column elution study⁵ using 0.5 and 0.05 M Na_2SO_4 in 0.05 M H_2SO_4 reveals that the amounts of hydroxyl ion released from the first two or three fractions were greater than those from the later fractions, because all the exchangeable ions were in hydroxyl form at the beginning. Almost all the hydroxyl ions were released completely after passage about 50 ml of the eluant.

Distribution coefficient (K_d): The apparent distribution coefficient (Table 1) of anions were determined at two different pH ranges 3.0-3.5 and 5.5-6.0 by batch operation⁶ using 0.5 g of exchanger (B_1) and (B_2) and keeping the anion concentration $3-3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$. The anions were estimated volumetrically^{1,6}. Phosphate was estimated spectrophotometrically⁷.

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS (K_d) OF ANIONS ON BASIC LEAD SULPHATE (B_1 AND B_2)

Anions	Temp. = $28 \pm 2^\circ$			
	K_d at pH 3.0-3.50		K_d at pH 5.50-6.0	
	B_1	B_2	B_1	B_2
CrO_4^{2-}	2.9×10^3	2.3×10^3	2.6×10^3	2.4×10^3
VO_4^{3-}	76.0	11.0	—	—
PO_4^{3-}	1.6×10^4	458.0	4.1×10^3	9.5
AsO_4^{3-}	97.0	62.5	72.5	64.2
AsO_3^{3-}	131.1	79.3	89.1	73.0
$Fe(OH)_4^{3-}$	1.1×10^3	580.0	580.0	385.7
$Fe(OH)_3^{2-}$	12.0	10.8	3.3	2.9
SCN^-	7.0	5.0	5.0	3.7
$Br(v)$	13.4	7.5	7.5	4.7
$I(v)$	3.3×10^3	1.1×10^3	200.0	256.8
$C_2O_4^{2-}$	836.0	1070.0	367.0	175.3
MnO_4^-	9.8	8.7	—	—

Chromate, phosphate, ferrocyanide, iodate and oxalate having very high K_d values could be sepa-

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